

Paper 2

**IMPACT OF DIGITALIZED EDUCATION ON
STUDENTS – A STUDY IN MANGALORE**

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Abstract

Education plays a prominent role in the present. Over a period of time numerous changes have taken place in all the sectors including the Education sector. Eventhough the evolution of Education primarily had an open space teaching with a relationship of ‘guru-shishya’, technology has changed the Education sector and has given a different shape to this sector in terms of accessibility, convenience and affordability. Conventionally there was only a uniform method of teaching that was chalk and talk but today education is provided through various teaching aids like projector and power point presentations, video learning, online classes, social networks, other online visual platforms etc. Most of the students have benefited from the digitalization of education, but in reality is this form of education helpful for the better prospects of students? The study relating to impact of digitalized education on students is aimed at analyzing the modern processes of education and its impact on the present day students.

1.Introduction

The concept of education had a long endeavor in the past and the same is expected in future. The conventional approach towards education as known empirically and also can be factually verified has seen a gradual decline and there is a transition towards digitized forms of education today in this turbulent globalized world. Education plays a vital role in the socio – cultural sphere especially in a country like India where the Hindu sect revere Goddess Saraswati’ that is the goddess of knowledge. Also historically in the Indian context especially in south India educating children was and is still considered a sacred duty among people of all religions.

However the digitalization of education has been synonymous with the term “modernization” of education and has given opportunities for many people to monetize on this sector. While it cannot be denied that digitization of education has opened the doors to affordability and limitless access to information there seems to be a gradual decline in the perspective of education in terms of its sacredness. While in developed states the digitization of education has absorbed well in the up gradation of quality of education it also becomes important to

have a study in the developing countries that adopt similar methods. This research paper has taken Mangalore a city in India for the same. Has Digitization worked well for students in Mangalore? Read below to find out.

2.Objectives

The main objectives of this research is to ascertain the impact of digitization of education on students with reference to the city of Mangalore. Besides the above mentioned the document seeks to attain the following:

- Affordability and accessibility of education post the digital era.
- Form a blueprint for further research by students/ research scholars in the field of education.
- Ascertain satisfaction of students with the digital modes of education.
- Pose a maverick view of the weightage of value of education in the present.

3.Methodology

For the purposes of this study, data and information has been collected from primary as well as secondary sources.

Primary Data: The data was collected through questionnaire and interview. A survey was conducted among the people of Mangalore. The respondents were asked to fill the questions from the scheduled questionnaire.

Secondary Data: Information was collected through Internet, magazines, research journals and articles.

- **Sample and Sample Size**

A sample size of 100 people has been taken through random sampling method. The study has been conducted among the people of the areas without considering their qualification or profession.

4.Review of literature

G.N. Wikramanayake: In his paper Impact of Digital Technology on Education describes the process of generation, creation and acquisition of knowledge through the technology. The paper also describes how technology is used to access and apply such knowledge. The paper relates how these technologies have been used in education and its impact in general. Using examples the paper highlights some of the changes that has taken place in the Sri Lankan education sector. He highlights that Paradigm shifts in today's world have identified the Machine / Industrial era being replaced by Technology / Information era. Similarly production process has moved from Products to Knowledge, Workplace has moved from Physical to Virtual and its focus has changed from Worker to Customer. His study is with reference to Sri Lanka.

Carlo Perrotta, Laura Czerniewicz and Helen Beetham in the paper ‘The rise of the video-recorder teacher: the sociomaterial construction of an educational actor’ draws on actor-network theory and on the sociology of cultural consumption to examine the phenomenon of corporate Massive Open Online Courses. Through an analysis of texts available in the public domain, the paper argues that over a short period (between 2012 and 2013) digitisation technology became associated with the emergence of a hybrid ‘actor’: the digital video-recorder teacher. A parallel is drawn between the ‘interactive affordances’ of digital instruction and the playback and cataloguing options that have contributed to shifts in television viewing habits. The digital video-recorder teacher is described as an artefact in the service of a postmodern project of self-improvement through cultural consumption, which recruits digitisation to meet a growing demand for ‘upgrades to the self’. In the conclusion, the paper explores how the study of digital education could benefit from an interface between sociomaterial studies and the sociology of culture.

Lousie Katz: In a report published in the conversation.com titled ‘Report shows consequences of monetised education system, but does little to dispel it’, the paper considers, among other things, how universities meet international students’ perceived needs and expectations, and the role of government in regulating quality. It rightly recommends that “learning standards have a greater role” and that education agents should have a lesser one in student recruitment. Explicitly it implies profitability has become a priority and not quality in providing education.

5.Charts

1.1) Method of teaching

1.2) Digitization and skill training

1.3) Mode of Digitisation

1.4) Applications Vs Internet sites

1.5) Digitisation and accessibility

6.Body and observations

This study is mainly empirical and after having a fruitful discussion with the students there were mixed responses but with regard to certain issues the responses recorded are as under:

CONVENTIONAL VS DIGITAL METHOD OF TEACHING: Around 75% of the students were in favour of digitized modes of education and argue that such modes are more attractive

as they use more diagrams, pictures and concise sentences in power point presentations. 10% of the students/ respondents do not find any changes in both the methods. The saying “Old wine in a new bottle” is an appropriate metaphor to describe their response. However 15% of the respondents still feel that conventional methods are better since it has worked for centuries and that a nation like India is not equipped to adopt digital platforms in the field of education.(Ref: Chart 1.1)

DIGITISATION AND SKILL TRAINING : With regard to skill training a 95% of the students still feel that the kind of sphere that digitized forms of education work in Mangalore don't equip students with the appropriate skills that they need for industry and say in this respect conventional and digitized forms of education have not integrated with industry and skill requirements. 10 respondents gave the example of Tally, SAP, and computers to learn not being used in colleges. (Ref: Chart 1.2)

MODE OF DIGITISATION: Around 85% of the respondents prefer mobile phones as an electronic device as compared to computers (15%). The prime argument being that smartphones are handy and that features like notes help them to record bookmarks. Portability of smartphones here is a clear advantage as compared to desktop computers or laptops. (Ref: Chart 1.3)

APPS VS INTERNET SITES: The internet has provided accessibility of information in 2 forms direct site login and the second one being accessibility of the application where applications of the requisite site can be downloaded and the icons will appear at the desktop/home screen. Which reduces the time lag required to access the required information. Applications like INSHORTS, BYJU'S, and INVEST YADNYA were some of the popular applications recommended by the respondents. Statistically 90% of the respondents favour the applications for accessing educational material. (Ref: Chart 1.4)

DIGITISATION AND ACCESSIBILITY: 80% of the respondents feel are of the opinion that digitization of education has bridged the gap between the seekers and suppliers of knowledge as information is available in a number of sources through the internet. Even colleges today are providing their students access to certain online educational sites subscribed by the college where students can get access to a number of books from various streams by Indian as well as foreign authors. But the remaining 20% argue that India still does not have the required infrastructure required and to an extent needs more time for digitized forms of education to be accessible. The main barrier being a number of people do not have access to smartphones still and need to be educated to use them. (Ref: Chart 1.5)

DIGITISATION VS AFFORDABILITY: There is an integration and a phenomenal inclusion of the 'have not's to the 'have's' due to digitization of education. Costs due to digitization have reduced the cost of educational products and services and has brought inclusion due to massive affordability. The only barrier the researchers have found in this paper is that payment of digitized educational products and services that is the mode of payment where there is a need to get greater financial inclusion to facilitate digital payments. Some respondents have also stated that digitized forms of education have been “Perverted” by certain coaching centres and institutes have created an impression with the help of the “Mad marketing machine” that expensive tutorials are due to digitized forms of education and

teachings that institutes not offering such services are underrated institutions. Digitization also gives room for “Yellow Educational Journals and educational potboilers.”

VALUE OF EDUCATION: More than 60% of the respondents agree that the “sacred value of education” as reflected in our culture, is diminishing but also agree that the commercial value of education is rapidly increasing which is a cause of worry. As rightly put forward by George Macaulay Trevelyan “Education has produced a vast population able to read, but unable to distinguish what is worth reading.”

Based on the above findings the researchers would like to propose the inverted cone, frustum cylinder theory.

“There is a saying in school you are taught a lesson and then you are put to the test, in life you are put to the test and then you learn a lesson. The truth is that practicality is what works in life.”

Figure 2.1 – cone cylinder

Figure 2.2 – frustum

Figure 2.3-

The above 3 diagrams represent 3 different scenarios. The first represents learning through the conventional system. The second diagram shows the digitized system and the 3rd diagram represents a model that needs to be developed to have a strong skill base in industry.

Background: This theory seeks to explain how educational models really equip today’s students to face industry.

Explanation: These 3 diagrams represent 3 structures with the bottom points/ surfaces representing the foundation (life/ industry skill) and the top surfaces representing the education system.

In the first diagram the student is sent into industry after graduating with the conventional educational method. The student is in a jeopardy as he enters industry as he is ill equipped with the skills he needs to be in industry. The knowledge he has amassed in his college/ educational institution is mostly not useful and thus is funneled down as the student goes to industry. Thus it can also be said that the foundation is not strong and the structural surface on top puts massive pressure on the structure to stand still. (Refer figure 2.1)

The second structure represents the digitized education system that is the present generation students. These represent both the students who have graduated from wholly and also from quasi – digitized platforms. Here too digitization of education has to some extent broadened the knowledge and skills the students need for industry. But still the foundation is under pressure and the structure is exerting massive pressure on the respondents to stand still (Refer figure 2.2).

The first two models still prevail in society but it is important to note that these systems have failed. Empirically when the students graduating from the above 2 systems/structures admitted that 95% of the information they get from the above systems don't work in industry and they find it hard to cope up with industry requirements. Some company “Trainers” have also confessed that they have to spend massive amounts to train employees (Students who have just graduated/ freshers) as the education system is not equipped to do so. When the researchers enquired about the role of the digitized education era, they mentioned that it could have helped in skill development but has been “Perverted” by greedy education monetary capitalists with the help of the “Mad marketing machine”.

The third structure represents a student who has been “learning while doing” that is learning while constantly interacting with industrialists and using digitized education platforms to update him with the latest trends. This model is still not in existence and presently there are very few students who might have been educated to be like the 3rd structure. Here the student is equipped with the necessary educational tools and skills to be applied in industry. As a result the foundation is strong and the structure stands comfortably. (Refer figure 2.3)

7. Suggestions

More than 90% of the students represent either the cone or the fructrum. To ensure that students are competitive and are trained for industry. Here are some suggestions to have improvements in digitized forms of education:

- New products like Educational games based on industry can be a great source of learning. Example – the cash flow game at www.richdad.com
- Conventional systems need to be more evolved to make education interesting. Digitized platforms and not curriculum in digitized platforms ought to be used to see growth in skill in India.
- Establishment of new digital training centres.
- Models and curriculum offered by certain digitized education platformssuch as simplus financial consultants and investyadnya academy can train students for the industry to an extent.

8. Conclusions

- Digitised forms of education have outperformed conventioanl methods.
- There needs to be safeguards in digitised forms of education from the mad marketing machine.
- Governments need to come up with legislations to encourage educational institutions to develop models like the “cylinder structure” as mentioaned above.

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